

(a) BaG_02-05 dt=1.12 us

(b) GaG_03-11 dt=1.37 us

(c) BpG_02-01 dt=1.27 us

(d) SaG_02-03 dt=930 ns

(e) PaG_01-06 dt=1.12 us

(f) ChG_02-15 dt=1.76 us

